

FABRICATION AND EVALIATION OF FRTP USING IN-SITU POLIMERIZATION PA 6 WITH VARTM

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1 Introduction

Thermoplastic resin, a matrix of fiber reinforced thermoplastic (FRTP), is composed of high polymers that remains highly viscous even at a higher temperature than its melting point. As a result, it need a higher temperature, a higher pressure and longer process time to allow it to bond with fibers, unlike fiber reinforced thermoset plastics (FRPs) to be easily molded due to the use of lower viscosity liquid resin as the matrix. In this paper, a fabrication method of the fiber reinforced thermoplastics using in-situ polymerization polyamide 6 as the matrix was presented. This method used a vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) without a large and special equipment. The polyamide 6 was converted from its monomer into thermoplastic polymer with ring-opening polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam during the molding process at a lower temperature than its melting temperature. Using glass fabrics, carbon fabrics and their hybrid fabrics with the in-situ polymerization PA 6, GFRTTP[1], CFRTP[2] and HFRTTP[3] were obtained respectively. These FRTP plates had no voids and unfilled parts because the ϵ -caprolactam had very low viscosity before polymerization. These FRTP not only exhibited superior mechanical properties, but also was suitable for high-speed molding, namely within one minute process time because it could be released from the mold without a cooling process.

2 Fabrication Method

2.1 Materials

The in-situ polymerization PA6 was obtained from ϵ -Caprolactam and sodium salt as an anionic catalyst and hexamethylene diisocyanate (HMDI) as an

active agent. In the CFRTP and the GFRTTP, CF fabrics (CF3302H, Toray Industries, Inc.) and GF fabrics (WEA22F-BX, Nitto Boseki Co., Ltd.) were used as the reinforcement, respectively. In the HFRTTP, the same CF and GF fabrics were used as the reinforcement.

2.2 Molding Method

The catalyst for anionic polymerization of ϵ -Caprolactam may lose its catalytic function due to the water in the air whereby polymerization may fail. Therefore, to fabricate the FRTP, it may be necessary to use the sealed (air tight) molding methods that can control the water content in the system This study selected the VaRTM method in which a simple vacuum pump was used as a resin infusion system for fabricating the FRTP.

Figure 1 shows a schematic view of the VaRTM molding system.

Figures 2 show the GFRTTP, CFRTP plates and the thickness direction view of HFRTTP. The dimensions of three FRTPs were 710 mm in length, 360 mm in width, 3 mm in thickness, 40mm in depth, 50 mm in flange width, respectively. In the HFRTTP, the CF fabrics were stacked upper 2 layers and lower 2 layers and the GF fabrics were stacked middle 10 layers. The volume fractions of three kinds of FRTP were 42 %.

Fig.1 Schematic view of VaRTM

(a) GFRTTP and CFRTP Plates

(b) Thickness View of HFRTTP

Figs 2 Three kinds of FRTP Plates

3. Bending Evaluation

Figure 3 shows the bending test results of both GFRTTPs. The pre suffix "I-" and "C-" meant the FRTPs fabricated by the in-situ polymerization PA 6 with the VaRTM and by the films of PA 6 with a hot press molding, respectively. The bending strength and modulus of the I-GFRTTP became the highest at the molding temperatures from 140°C to 160°C. This dependency of the bending strength and modulus on the molding temperature seems to correlate with the content of un-reacted monomer in the matrix. The I-GFRTTP fabricated at the temperatures from 180 to 200°C had a larger percentage of the un-reacted monomer. This un-reacted monomer contained in the matrix seems to lead insufficient polymerization

Fig. 3 Bending Properties of Both GFRTTP

and then to be lower mechanical strength. Based on these bending test results, we find that there is an optimum range of molding temperature of the in-situ polymerization PA 6.

The bending strength and modulus of the C-GFRTTP used already polymerized PA 6 as the matrix was approximately the same as the I-GFRTTP molded at the temperature from 140°C to 160°C in terms of both the bending strength and modulus.

Figure 4 shows the representative stress-stain of the I-CFRTP, the I-GFRTTP and the I-HFRTTP fabricated at the molding temperature of 140°C. The stress of the I-HFRTTP increased approximately linearly with the strain and the value of failure was same as that of the I-CFRTP. The experimental results of the bending strength and modulus (485MPa and 35.9GPa) approximately agreed with the theoretical values (487MPa and 33.6GPa) because no delamination between the CF and GF fabrics at the compression side.

Fig.4 Relations of Bending Stress to Bending Strain for Three Kind of FRTP

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